

Assessment of Coping Strategies Towards Inflation on Agricultural Input Costs Among Farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Small-scale farming households in Nigeria depend heavily on agriculture as their primary source of income and livelihood. However, persistent inflation, particularly the rising cost of essential inputs, poses a major threat to smallholder farming. This study assessed the coping strategies employed by farmers in Kwara State in response to increasing input costs, focusing on their socioeconomic characteristics, perceptions of inflation, coping strategies adopted, and challenges limiting these strategies. A survey-based descriptive research design was used to collect data from 120 respondents selected through a multistage sampling technique across Ilorin East, Offa, and Oyun Local Government Areas due to their diverse agricultural activities and varying exposure to rising input costs. Structured interview schedules were employed for data collection, while descriptive statistics (frequency counts, means, percentages, and ranks) and inferential analysis (multiple regression) were used. Findings revealed that 86.7% of farmers perceived inflation as a serious threat to their farming activities, with 56.7% reporting it as a major threat to their business. Common coping strategies included spreading input purchases over time (97.5%), changing cropping patterns (92.5%), and leasing or sharing equipment (88.3%). Major challenges identified were reduced income (88.3%), high transportation costs (80.0%), and unpredictable weather patterns (75.8%). The study concludes that although farmers adopt adaptive measures to manage inflation, structural constraints limit their effectiveness. It therefore recommends strengthening youth-centered agricultural empowerment through the CYIAP platform, promoting accessible input-support schemes, and enhancing cooperative participation to help farmers cope effectively with rising input costs.

Keywords: Agricultural inputs, Smallholder farmers, Inflation, Coping strategies

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains a critical pillar of Nigeria's economy, providing employment, food security, and contributing significantly to Gross Domestic Product (Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), 2021). However, persistent inflation, especially in agricultural input markets, poses serious threats to smallholder productivity. Rising costs of fertilizers, fuel, seeds, and machinery have undermined profitability and forced farmers into adopting coping mechanisms that often sacrifice productivity (World Bank, 2022). From 2020 to 2022, fertilizer prices increased by over 35%, while seed prices rose by 25% (Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), 2022). These changes have disproportionately affected rural farmers in Kwara State. Understanding how farmers perceive and respond to inflation is essential for developing targeted policies that enhance resilience, safeguard livelihoods, and maintain food security.

Sequel to the rise in the cost of agricultural inputs, it has led to significant rise in prices of agricultural commodities in Nigeria. For example, the cost of food in Nigeria increased by 37.77% in September 2023 over the same month in the previous year (Nigeria

Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2024). NBS further stated that the food inflation in Nigeria averaged 13.72% from 1996 to 2024, reaching an all-time high of 40.87% in June 2024 and a record low of -17.50% in January 2000 (NBS, 2024). As prices for inputs rise, farmers may be forced to make difficult decisions about how to allocate their limited resources (Aliyi et al., 2021). Understanding the effect of inflation on agricultural input costs is crucial for ensuring food security, rural development, and farms' sustainability. Nigeria's economy depends heavily on agriculture, but little is known about how inflation especially impacts farmers' costs of agricultural inputs in Kwara State. This situation makes it more challenging to enact principles and implement programmes that will benefit farmers and boost agricultural productivity. To bridge this knowledge gap, the study aims to clarify the challenges faced by farmers and assist in directing decisions regarding poverty alleviation, agricultural development, and inflation control by examining the relationship between inflation and the price of agricultural inputs. This study focuses on understanding these challenges in detail, examining how inflation influences farmers' choices, their financial health, and the sustainability of their operations.

This study holds significant relevance as it explores the critical relationship between inflation and agricultural input costs faced by farmers in Kwara State. By examining how inflation influences the prices of essential agricultural inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, and machinery this research aims to provide valuable insights into the economic pressures confronting farmers in the State. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing effective policies that can help mitigate the adverse effects of inflation on agricultural production.

The findings will equip authorities with the knowledge necessary to create targeted interventions, such as subsidies or price stabilization mechanisms, which can alleviate the financial burden on farmers. This support is vital not only for maintaining farmers' livelihoods but also for ensuring food security in a region where agriculture is a primary source of income and sustenance. Additionally, the study will enhance stakeholders' understanding of inflation's impact, empowering them to design better financial strategies and farming practices to mitigate the rising costs.

Objectives of the study

1. assess the farmers' perception towards inflation on agricultural input costs in kwara State;
2. identify the coping strategies adopted by farmers to mitigate the effects of inflation on agricultural input costs in kwara state; and
3. identify the challenges limiting the coping strategies adopted towards inflation on agricultural input costs in kwara State.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Kwara State using a three-stage sampling procedure. In the first stage, three Local Government Areas namely Ilorin East, Offa, and Oyun, were randomly selected from the sixteen LGAs in the state due to their diverse agricultural activities and their varying levels of exposure to rising input costs. The second stage involved a random selection

of two communities from each Local Government; Oke Ose and Oke oyi from Ilorin east, Kanmonmu and Kere Aje from Offa, Ijagbo and igbonna from Oyun. The third stage involved the random selection of 32 respondents in Ilorin east, 48 respondents in Offa and 40 respondents in Oyun Local Government, a total number of 120 respondents were selected for this study. Data collection was carried out using a structured interview schedule to elicit information from the selected farmers. The data obtained from the field was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Descriptive tools such as frequency count, percentages, mean, ranks and inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Farmers' Perception towards Inflation on Agricultural Input Costs

The results show that farmers in Kwara State see inflation in agricultural input costs as a serious problem. Ranked first, 86.7% of farmers strongly agreed that farm profits have dropped significantly due to inflation. Second, more than half (56.7%) said that inflation is a major threat to the survival of their farms. Many farmers also reported having to reduce their farm output (46.7%) and cut down their farm size (51.7%), ranked third and fourth, respectively. About 36% indicated that their debt has increased, while 44.2% noted that household food security has been affected. Fewer farmers felt that the quality of inputs had declined or that the government was doing enough to address rising costs, and only a tiny number (2.5%) believed they could adapt successfully to changing input prices. These findings are consistent with Mansoor and Shahzad (2025), who reported that input price inflation is widely felt by farmers and significantly reduces profitability and adaptive capacity. Overall, the results highlight that inflation is putting farmers under serious financial and operational pressure, threatening both their productivity and livelihoods.

Table 1: Farmers' Perception towards Inflation on Agricultural Input Costs

S/N	Farmers' perception towards Inflation	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean (\bar{x})	Rank
1	Farm profits have decreased significantly due to Inflation	104(86.7)	12(9.9)	2(1.7)	0(0)	2(1.7)	4.82	1 st
2	Inflation is a major threat to my farming business	68(56.7)	41(34.2)	4(3.3)	6(5.0)	1(0.8)	4.41	2 nd
3	Inflation has forced me to reduce my farm output	56(46.7)	56(46.7)	2(1.7)	5(4.2)	1(0.8)	4.34	3 rd
4	Inflation has resulted in a reduction of farm size	62(51.7)	46(38.3)	2(1.7)	10(8.3)	0(0)	4.33	4 th
5	Inflation has led to an increase in the debt burden	43(35.8)	39(32.5)	1(0.8)	26(21.7)	11(9.2)	3.64	5 th
6	Inflation has affected my household's food security	20(16.7)	53(44.2)	17(14.2)	25(20.8)	5(4.2)	3.48	6 th
7	The quality of agricultural inputs has decreased as prices increased	19(15.8)	13(10.8)	16(13.3)	50(41.7)	22(18.3)	2.64	7 th
8	The government is doing enough to address the issue of rising input costs	15(12.5)	30(25.0)	8(6.7)	31(25.8)	36(30.0)	2.64	7 th
9	My farming practices are sustainable despite rising input costs	8(6.7)	19(15.8)	14(11.7)	56(46.7)	23(19.2)	2.44	9 th
10	I am able to adapt to the changing prices of agricultural inputs	0(0)	3(2.5)	9(7.5)	65(54.2)	43(35.8)	1.77	10 th

Source: Field survey, 2025

Coping Strategies Adopted By Farmers to Mitigate the Effect of Inflation

The result in Table 2 revealed that farmers adopted a variety of coping strategies to counter the effects of inflation. The most prevalent (97.5%) were spreading input purchases over time changing cropping patterns (92.5%), and leasing or sharing equipment instead of outright purchase (88.3%). Other widely used

measures included reducing farm size (85%) and seeking alternative financing (79.2%). In contrast, fewer farmers joined cooperatives (44.2%) or opted for cheaper seed varieties (24.2%). These findings are similar from Ogheneruemu and Owosho (2023), who observed that cooperative membership and access to credit were key coping mechanisms among Nigerian households facing agricultural shocks

Table 2: Coping Strategies Adopted By Farmers to Mitigate the Effect of Inflation

S/N	Coping Strategies Adopted	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	farm size reduction	102(85)	18(15)
2	Reduction of fertilizer or pesticide application	92(76.7)	28(23.3)
3	Changing cropping patterns	111(92.5)	9(7.5)
4	Use of friends/family for labour	60(50.0)	60(50.0)
5	Consider alternative sources of financing	95(79.2)	25(20.8)
6	Joining a cooperative or farmers association to benefit from bulk purchase	53(44.2)	67(55.8)
7	Using cheaper seed varieties	29(24.2)	91(75.8)
8	Leasing or sharing farming equipment instead of purchasing new ones	106(88.3)	14(11.7)
9	Seeking government support	70(58.3)	50(41.7)
10	Spread out input purchase over time	117(97.5)	3(2.5)

Source: Field survey, 2025

Challenges Limiting the Coping Strategies Adopted

The major constraints limiting farmers' coping strategies were reduced income (88.3%) and high transportation costs (80%), followed by unpredictable weather patterns (75.8%). Labour scarcity, insufficient

government support, and poor access to credit also significantly hindered adaptation. These findings support Ogheneruemu and Owosho (2023), who observed that income shocks and rising market costs undermine resilience, and Ambler et al. (2025), who reported that limited credit access remains a persistent bottleneck for Nigerian smallholders.

Table 3: Challenges Limiting the Coping Strategies Adopted

S/N	Challenges limiting the coping strategies	S (%)	MS (%)	NS (%)	Mean (\bar{x})	Rank
1	Reduced income	106(88.3)	14(11.7)	0(0)	2.88	1st
2	High transportation cost	96(80.0)	21(17.5)	3(2.5)	2.78	2nd
3	Unpredictable weather patterns	91(75.8)	22(18.3)	7(5.8)	2.68	3rd
4	Scarcity of labour	70(58.3)	33(27.5)	17(14.2)	2.44	4th
5	Insufficient government support	75(62.5)	26(21.7)	19(15.8)	2.40	5th
6	Poor access to credit facilities	61(50.8)	49(40.8)	10(8.3)	2.43	6th
7	Lack of access to climate information	45(37.5)	50(41.7)	25(20.8)	2.17	7th
8	Limited access to alternative financing	48(40.0)	35(29.2)	37(30.8)	2.09	8th
9	Shortage of quality seeds	38(31.7)	19(15.8)	63(52.5)	1.77	9th
10	Inadequate storage facilities for inputs	25(20.8)	21(17.5)	74(61.7)	1.61	10th

Source: Field survey, 2025

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that farmers in Kwara State see inflation in input costs as a major threat, leading to reduced profits, smaller farm sizes, lower output, and rising debt, with very few able to adapt effectively. Although they adopted coping strategies such as spreading input purchases and adjusting cropping

patterns, these were limited by low income, high transport costs, labour shortages, and poor access to credit. The study therefore recommends providing affordable credit, encouraging cooperative membership, improving government support, enhancing rural infrastructure, and expanding access to climate information and alternative financing to strengthen farmers' resilience to inflation.

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